

FP6-511678

ORCHESTRA

**Open Architecture and Spatial Data Infrastructure for
Risk Management**

Integrated Project

Priority 2.3.2.9 Improving Risk Management

WP3.6 – OA Service Implementation

**Implementation Specification of the Authentication
Service**

Revision [1.1 / 1.3]

Document Control Page

Title	Implementation Specification of the Authentication Service
Creator	Berlinghoff, Thomas Environmental Informatics Group
Subject	WP3.6 – OA Service Implementation
Description	This document defines a platform specific implementation specification of the Authentication Service. The Authentication Service is part of the ORCHESTRA UAA concept, and assures someone is what he pretends to be.
Publisher	ORCHESTRA consortium
Contributor	Berlinghoff, Thomas Environmental Informatics Group Fischer, Julian Environmental Informatics Group Ma, Wenjie Environmental Informatics Group
Date	2007-01-28
Type	Text
Format	application/msword
Identifier	http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=19463
Source	Not applicable
Language	en-GB.
Relation	None
Coverage	ORCHESTRA Consortium
Rights	
Deliverable number	D3.6.4
Work-Package contributing to the Deliverable	WP3.6
Contractual Date of Delivery	
Actual Date of Delivery	
Audience	<input type="checkbox"/> public <input type="checkbox"/> restricted <input type="checkbox"/> internal

Version number	1.1 / 1.3
Date	2007-12-03
Modified by	Ma, Wenjie Environmental Informatics Group
Comments	
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft

	<input type="checkbox"/> WP leader accepted <input type="checkbox"/> SP leader accepted <input type="checkbox"/> Technical supervisor accepted <input type="checkbox"/> Quality checked <input type="checkbox"/> Project coordinator accepted
<p>Action requested</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> to be revised by partners involved in the preparation of the deliverable <input type="checkbox"/> for approval of the WP leader <input type="checkbox"/> for approval of the SP leader <input type="checkbox"/> for approval of the Technical Supervisor <input type="checkbox"/> for approval of the Quality Manager <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> for approval of the Project Coordinator Deadline for action: YYYY-MM-DD

Revision History

Revision	Date	Sections changed	Description
0.1 / 1.1	2006-08-10	All	Initial release
0.3 / 1.1	2006-10-03	All	
0.5 / 1.1	2006-10-08	Appendix B	Update of XML and WSDL documents.
0.6 / 1.1	2006-10-19	4, 6.1.3, 6.1.4, 6.2	Incorporate changes made to the abstract specification.
0.7 / 1.1	2006-10-24	6	Adapted WSDL and XML documents.
0.8 / 1.1	2006-12-18	6, 7	Update of XML Schemas.
0.9 / 1.1	2007-01-18	All	Incorporated comments.
0.9.1 / 1.1	2007-01-19	4.5	Description of the login operation edited.
1.0 / 1.1	2007-01-28	Annex A	Updated WSDL and XML Schemas to reflect the new namespaces.
1.1 / 1.3	2007-12-03	All	Update new template

Table of Contents

i.	Preface.....	8
ii.	Relations to the platform-neutral OA Service Specification.....	8
iii.	Future work.....	8
1	Scope.....	9
2	Conventions.....	10
2.1	UML Notation.....	10
2.2	Conformance.....	10
2.2.1	Conformance to the Platform and the OA.....	10
2.2.2	Conformance to the abstract specification of the Authentication Service.....	10
2.3	Used parts of other documents.....	10
3	Mapping from an Abstract Specification.....	11
3.1	Service Capabilities Interface.....	11
3.1.1	getCapabilities Operation.....	11
3.1.1.1	OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest Parameter Type.....	11
3.1.1.2	OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse Parameter Type.....	12
3.1.1.3	OA_MI_Service_SpecificCapabilities Parameter Type.....	12
3.2	Authentication Service Interface.....	13
3.2.1	activatePrincipal Operation.....	13
3.2.2	deactivatePrincipal Operation.....	13
3.2.3	login Operation.....	14
3.2.4	createPrincipal Operation.....	14
3.2.5	removePrincipal Operation.....	14
3.2.6	updatePrincipal Operation.....	15
3.2.7	addCredentials Operation.....	15
3.2.8	updateCredentials Operation.....	15
3.2.9	removeCredentials Operation.....	15
3.2.10	verifySessionInformation Operation.....	16
3.2.11	getPrincipals Operation.....	16
4	Platform-specific specification.....	17
4.1	Authentication Service Overview.....	17
4.2	Specification of a Profile of Parameter Types used by the Authentication Service.....	17

4.3	Specification of the getCapabilities Operation.....	19
4.4	Specification of the activatePrincipal Operation.....	21
4.5	Specification of the deactivatePrincipal Operation.....	23
4.6	Specification of the login Operation.....	25
4.7	Specification of the createPrincipal Operation	27
4.8	Specification of the removePrincipal Operation	29
4.9	Specification of the updatePrincipal Operation	31
4.10	Specification of the addCredentials Operation	33
4.11	Specification of the updateCredentials Operation	35
4.12	Specification of the removeCredentials Operation	37
4.13	Specification of the verifySessionInformation Operation.....	39
4.14	Specification of the getPrincipals Operation	41
5	Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.....	43
5.1	XML Schema Documents.....	43
5.1.1	authentication_exceptions.xsd.....	43
5.1.2	authentication_types.xsd.....	45
5.1.3	authentication_requests.xsd	50
5.2	WSDL Document.....	53
6	Appendix B: UML Model.....	68
6.1	Static model.....	68
6.2	Dynamic model.....	69

Tables

Table 1: Mapping of operations of the Service Capabilities interface.....	11
Table 2: Mapping of parameters used by the getCapabilities operation	11
Table 3: Mapping of attributes used in getCapabilities request parameter	12
Table 4: Mapping of attributes used in getCapabilities return parameter	12
Table 5: Mapping of attributes used in parameter OA_MI_Service_SpecificCapabilities	12
Table 6: Mapping of operations of the Authentication Service interface	13
Table 7: Mapping of parameters used by the activatePrincipal operation.....	13
Table 8: Mapping of parameters used by the deactivatePrincipal operation.....	14
Table 9: Mapping of parameters used by the login operation	14
Table 10: Mapping of parameters used by the createPrincipal operation	14
Table 11: Mapping of parameters used by the removePrincipal operation	14
Table 12: Mapping of parameters used by the updatePrincipal operation	15
Table 13: Mapping of parameters used by the addCredentials operation.....	15
Table 14: Mapping of parameters used by the updateCredentials operation.....	15
Table 15: Mapping of parameters used by the removeCredentials operation.....	16
Table 16: Mapping of parameters used by the verifySessionInformation operation	16
Table 17: Mapping of parameters used by the getPrincipals operation	16
Table 18: Summary of Service Operations.....	17
Table 19: XML Types.....	18
Table 20: Specification of the getCapabilities Operation	20
Table 21: Specification of the activatePrincipal Operation	21
Table 22: Specification of the deactivatePrincipal Operation	23
Table 23: Specification of the login Operation	26
Table 24: Specification of the createPrincipal Operation.....	27
Table 25: Specification of the removePrincipal Operation.....	30
Table 26: Specification of the updatePrincipal Operation.....	31
Table 27: Specification of the addCredentials Operation	34
Table 28: Specification of the updateCredentials Operation	35
Table 29: Specification of the removeCredentials Operation	37
Table 30: Specification of the verifySessionInformation Operation	39
Table 31: Specification of the getPrincipals Operation	41

i. **Preface**

The Authentication Service is based on the abstract specification of the Authentication Service, Version 1.3.

This implementation specification describes the implementation of the Authentication Service with respect to the requirements of pilot implementations. Therefore currently only the username-password authentication mechanism using a MySQL database as persistent storage backend¹ is supported.

For a detailed description of the Authentication Service please refer to the correspondent abstract specification.

ii. **Relations to the platform-neutral OA Service Specification**

Derivations from the abstract service specification

The implementation specification of the Authentication Service does not require derivations from the abstract specification to accommodate the technical contents of this document.

Modifications of the abstract service specification

Modifications of the abstract specification of the Authentication Service are not necessary.

iii. **Future work**

Improvements in this document are desirable to support additional principal/credential types and hence additional authentication mechanisms. The support of additional types is realised through additional handlers.

See the "UAA Developers Guide" for more information about implementing handlers.

¹ required for storing principals and credentials

Implementation Specification of the Au- thentication Service

1 Scope

This document defines an implementation specification of the Authentication Service for the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform 1.1.1 and is based on the Template for the Implementation Specification of ORCHESTRA Services version 1.3. It specifies the interfaces implemented by the discussed service as well as their main purposes in relation to a concrete OSN. It provides a formal description of the implemented operations according to the rules defined in the specification of the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform.

The current implementation follows a framework based approach including a reference implementation for all required components. The implemented components restrict the usage of authentication mechanisms to a username-password based approach, storing required information in a relational database. Restrictions given by the current implementation follow the requirements of the pilots.

Further principal/credential types and hence authentication mechanisms may be supported by implementing additional handlers. Please refer to the "UAA Developers Guide 0.3" for more information.

2 Conventions

2.1 UML Notation

All software engineering diagrams in this specification are presented using the Unified Modelling Language (UML) version 2.0 as the conceptual schema language.

2.2 Conformance

2.2.1 Conformance to the Platform and the OA

This implementation specification is conformant to the ORCHESTRA Meta-Model for Services (OMM-Service) and the specification of the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform.

The data model defined in this document is compliant to the ORCHESTRA Meta-Model for Information (OMM-Info) and its platform specific representation.

The platform specific representation of the data model in XML Schema defined according to the rules of the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform is ISO/DIS 19136 Geographic information - Geography Markup Language (GML) Version 2.1.2.

The following exception that is in compliance with platform rules apply:

1. Non-geographic Features (“normal classes”) are not derived from GML base types

The Web service specifications presented in this document are compliant to WSDL Version 1.1 with SOAP Version 1.1 HTTP binding.

The possible bindings are:

1. SOAP Version 1.1 HTTP binding

The binding is specified in chapter Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

The message style that shall be used is document/literal non-wrapped. This has the consequence that each operation takes only one single input parameter (an XML element). This XML element is referenced in the wsdl:message which has only one wsdl:part.

The mapping of an operation with multiple parameters to an operation with one single request parameter is subject to the chapter Mapping from an Abstract Specification.

2.2.2 Conformance to the abstract specification of the Authentication Service

According to the conformance clause of the abstract specification of the Authentication Service, this implementation specification can be considered conformant to the abstract specification.

The derivations from the abstract specification and from the mapping rules are documented in chapter Mapping from an Abstract Specification.

2.3 Used parts of other documents

This document does not use significant parts of other documents.

3 Mapping from an Abstract Specification

The following subchapters defines the mapping between the abstract specification of the Authentication Service and the platform specification for the “ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform”.

3.1 Service Capabilities Interface

The following table lists the mapping between operations of the Service Capabilities Interface:

Abstract Specification	Implementation Specification	Note
getCapabilities	getCapabilities	

Table 1: Mapping of operations of the Service Capabilities interface

The implementation specification of the Service Capabilities Interface is a 1:1 mapping from the abstract interface specification and is syntactically and semantically equivalent, except for service specific capabilities, to the specification of the Service Capabilities Interface.

The implementation specification of the Service Capabilities Interface does not follow strictly the mapping rules of the Platform Specification.

All operations of this interface have exactly 0 or 1 input parameter. A mapping of multiple operation parameters to one single request parameter as required by the document/literal message style is therefore not required.

3.1.1 getCapabilities Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the getCapabilities operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
request	OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest	O	request	OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest	M	(1)
return	OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse	M	return	OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse	M	(2)

Table 2: Mapping of parameters used by the getCapabilities operation

- (1) The request parameter shall be mandatory in the implementation of the getCapabilities operation.
- (2) Note that the type OA_CapabilitiesDocument of the abstract specification has been renamed to OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse for clarity.

3.1.1.1 OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest Parameter Type

This subchapter defines the mapping of the request parameter of the getCapabilities operation.

Attribute of Abstract Spec.	Parameter of Implementation Spec.	Note
-----------------------------	-----------------------------------	------

acceptFormats	OA_MimeType[0..*]	O	acceptFormats	OA_MimeType[0..*]	O	(1)
acceptSpec Versions	CharacterString[0..*]	O	acceptSpec Versions	CharacterString[0..*]	O	
sections	OA_CapabilitiesSections	O	sections	OA_Capabilities Sections	O	

Table 3: Mapping of attributes used in getCapabilities request parameter

(1) Independent of the contents of the acceptFormats attribute, the returned capabilities can always be formatted according to the default MIME type which is defined as “text/xml”.

3.1.1.2 OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse Parameter Type

This subchapter defines the mapping of the return parameter of the getCapabilities operation.

Attribute of Abstract Spec.			Parameter of Implementation Spec.			Note
capability Sections	Binary	M	capability Sections	xsd:anyType	M	(1)
format	OA_MimeType	M	format	OA_MimeType	M	(2)
schemaName	OA_CapabilitiesSchema	M	schemaName	OA_Capabilities Schema	M	
version	CharacterString	M	version	xsd:string	M	

Table 4: Mapping of attributes used in getCapabilities return parameter

- (1) The XML Schema type anyType is used in the implementation specification to allow the capabilities to be structured according to a certain XML Schema which is not predefined here. The capabilities shall be structured according to the schema indicated by the value of the schemaName attribute.
- (2) The value of the format attribute may always denote the default MIME Type “text/xml” indicating that the capabilities are formatted in XML.

3.1.1.3 OA_MI_Service_SpecificCapabilities Parameter Type

Since OA_CapabilitiesDocument contains common service capabilities (OA_MI_ServiceCommonCapabilities) and service specific capabilities (OA_MI_ServiceSpecificCapabilities) this subchapter defines the mapping of the OA_MI_ServiceSpecificCapabilities.

Attribute of Abstract Spec.			Parameter of Implementation Spec.			Note
supportedAuthenticationMechanisms	OA_MI_Authentication Mechanism	M	supportedAuthenticationMechanisms	OA_MI_AuthenticationMechanism	M	

Table 5: Mapping of attributes used in parameter OA_MI_Service_SpecificCapabilities

3.2 Authentication Service Interface

The following table lists the mapping between operations of the Authentication Service Interface:

Abstract Specification	Implementation Specification	Note
login	login	
createPrincipal	createPrincipal	
removePrincipal	removePrincipal	
updatePrincipal	updatePrincipal	
addCredentials	addCredentials	
updateCredentials	updateCredentials	
removeCredentials	removeCredentials	
deactivatePrincipal	deactivatePrincipal	
activatePrincipal	activatePrincipal	
verifySessionInformation	verifySessionInformation	
getPrincipals	getPrincipals	

Table 6: Mapping of operations of the Authentication Service interface

The implementation specification of the Authorisation Interface is a 1:1 mapping from the abstract interface specification and is syntactically and semantically equivalent to the specification of the Authorisation Interface.

3.2.1 activatePrincipal Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the activatePrincipal operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
principal	OA_Principal	M	request	activatePrincipalRequest	M	

Table 7: Mapping of parameters used by the activatePrincipal operation

3.2.2 deactivatePrincipal Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the deactivatePrincipal operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
principal	OA_Principal	M	request	deactivatePrincipalRequest	M	

Table 8: Mapping of parameters used by the deactivatePrincipal operation

3.2.3 login Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the login operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
principal	OA_Principal	M	request	loginRequest	M	
credential	OA_Credentials	M				
sessionInformation	OA_SessionInformation	M				
response	OA_AuthenticationSessionInformation	M	response	OA_AuthenticationSessionInformation	M	

Table 9: Mapping of parameters used by the login operation

3.2.4 createPrincipal Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the createPrincipal operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
principal	OA_Principal	M	request	createPrincipalRequest	M	

Table 10: Mapping of parameters used by the createPrincipal operation

3.2.5 removePrincipal Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the removePrincipal operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
principal	OA_Principal	M	request	removePrincipalRequest	M	

Table 11: Mapping of parameters used by the removePrincipal operation

3.2.6 updatePrincipal Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the updatePrincipal operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
principal	OA_Principal	M	request	updatePrincipalRequest	M	

Table 12: Mapping of parameters used by the updatePrincipal operation

3.2.7 addCredentials Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the addCredentials operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
principal	OA_Principal	M	request	addCredentialsRequest	M	
credentials	OA_Credentials	M				
response	OA_Credentials	M	Not applicable	Not applicable		

Table 13: Mapping of parameters used by the addCredentials operation

3.2.8 updateCredentials Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the updateCredentials operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
principal	OA_Principal	M	request	updateCredentialsRequest	M	
credentials	OA_Credentials	M				

Table 14: Mapping of parameters used by the updateCredentials operation

3.2.9 removeCredentials Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the removeCredentials operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
principal	OA_Principal	M	request	removeCredentialsRe-	M	

				quest		
--	--	--	--	-------	--	--

Table 15: Mapping of parameters used by the removeCredentials operation

3.2.10 verifySessionInformation Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the verifySessionInformation operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
principal	OA_Authenticated-Principal	M	request	verifySessionInformationRequest	M	
response	Boolean	M	response	xsd:boolean	M	

Table 16: Mapping of parameters used by the verifySessionInformation operation

3.2.11 getPrincipals Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the getPrincipals operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
query	OA_Query	O	request	getPrincipalsRequest	M	
response	Sequence<OA_Principal>	M	response	SequenceOfOA_Principal	M	

Table 17: Mapping of parameters used by the getPrincipals operation

4 Platform-specific specification

4.1 Authentication Service Overview

For a detailed description of the AuthenticationService Interface refer to the abstract specification of the Authentication Service.

The following table lists the operations of the Authentication Service and specifies whether they are adapted from another implementation specification.

Name	Overwrite
getCapabilities	Adapted from the specification of the OA Basic Service. Enhanced by service specific capabilities.
login	Copied from the specification of the AuthenticationService Interface.
addPrincipal	Copied from the specification of the AuthenticationService Interface.
removePrincipal	Copied from the specification of the AuthenticationService Interface.
updatePrincipal	Copied from the specification of the AuthenticationService Interface.
addCredentials	Copied from the specification of the AuthenticationService Interface.
updateCredentials	Copied from the specification of the AuthenticationService Interface.
removeCredentials	Copied from the specification of the AuthenticationService Interface.
deactivatePrincipal	Copied from the specification of the AuthenticationService Interface.
activatePrincipal	Copied from the specification of the AuthenticationService Interface.
verifySessionInformation	Copied from the specification of the AuthenticationService Interface.
getPrincipals	Copied from the specification of the AuthenticationService Interface.

Table 18: Summary of Service Operations.

The formal platform-specific description of the Authentication Service can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

4.2 Specification of a Profile of Parameter Types used by the Authentication Service

The following data types are used within this specification:

Name	Usage	User Defined	from Profile
------	-------	--------------	--------------

ServiceSpecificCapabilities	O	Yes	OA Basic Service
OA_Credentials	I	Yes	OA Types
OA_PasswordCredentials	I	Yes	OA Types
OA_Principal	I	No	OA Types
OA_UsernamePrincipal	I	Yes	OA Types
OA_AuthenticationSessionInformation	O	Yes	OA Types
OA_FeatureCollection	O	No	OA Types
OA_CapabilitiesDocument	O	No	OA MI Types
OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest	I	No	OA Types
OA_Query	I	No	OA Types
OA_VersionNegotiationFailed	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_UnsupportedSchema	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_InvalidParameterValue	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_MissingParameterValue	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_NoApplicableCode	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_InternalError	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_NoSuchPrincipalException	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_PrincipalNotFoundException	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_AuthenticationFailedException	E	Yes	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_PermissionDeniedException	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types

Table 19: XML Types

The formal specification in XML of these types can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

This service specification does not define user defined Types.

4.3 Specification of the getCapabilities Operation

The mandatory getCapabilities operation informs the client of the capabilities of an ORCHESTRA Service Instance (OSI). This operation takes into account that in addition to capabilities that are common to all ORCHESTRA Services an ORCHESTRA Service may provide a specific set of capabilities. Furthermore, this operation allows the capabilities to be delivered according to different service meta-information schemas. This implementation specification therefore does not prescribe a certain schema to be used for the service capabilities. One or several schemas to be supported as well as a default schema have to be defined in the context of an OSN.

A service meta-information document is returned to the requesting client, either complete or including selected parts according to the given sections in the request.

A request to perform the getCapabilities operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 11. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional | mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	modified			
Overrides	not applicable			
Preconditions	none			
Post conditions	Service meta-information document returned to requesting client, either complete or including selected parts according to the given sections in the request			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest	mandatory	Specifies the parts of the meta-information to be returned. If absent, all parts shall be returned using the default schema.
Returns	Type		Description	
	OA_CapabilitiesDocument		Service capabilities of the specific OSI for the specific ORCHESTRA Service.	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	

	OA_InternalError	A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)
	OA_VersionNegotiationFailed	List of versions in acceptSpecVersions parameter value in the getCapabilities request did not include any version supported by the OSI.
	OA_UnsupportedSchema	The sections parameter in the getCapabilities request referred to a schema unsupported by the OSI.

Table 20: Specification of the getCapabilities Operation

Note that in contrast to the abstract specification the request parameter is mandatory in order to simplify the mapping to the platform.

According to the abstract specification the request parameter consists of the following elements:

- acceptFormats: Optional parameter containing a prioritized sequence of zero or more response formats desired by the caller, with preferred formats listed first. The formats are to be expressed in terms of MIME types. Independent of the contents of this element, the returned capabilities can always be formatted according to the default MIME type which is defined as “text/xml”.
- acceptSpecVersions: Optional parameter containing a prioritized sequence of zero or more specification versions of the ORCHESTRA service accepted by the client, with the preferred versions listed first. If no versions are included in the request, the highest version that the service supports shall be used.
- sections: Optional parameter specifying the schema for service meta-information according to which the capabilities shall be structured. In addition the names of requested sections in the complete set of meta-information elements can be listed. If absent, the complete service capabilities shall be returned structured according to a default schema which has to be defined in the context of an OSN.

According to the abstract specification the return parameter consists of the following elements:

- capabilitySections: Capabilities as meta-information document which is internally structured according to the indicated format and the indicated schema. It is either complete or includes only selected parts according to the given sections in the request.
- format: MIME type of the format in which the capabilities are returned as value of the capabilitySections parameter. The value of this attribute may always denote the default MIME Type “text/xml” indicating that the capabilities are formatted in XML.
- schemaName: Schema according to which the capabilities are returned. The value is the same as the one contained in the sections parameter of the request. If not explicitly included in the request, the value indicates the default schema.
- version: Version number of the specification to which the delivered service meta-information document is conform.

The formal platform-specific specification of the getCapabilities operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="getCapabilitiesRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="request" element="oab:OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getCapabilitiesResponse">
  <wsdl:part name="return" element="oab:OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

4.4 Specification of the activatePrincipal Operation

The optional activatePrincipal operation activates an existing principal. Only active principals can be authenticated.

A request to perform the activatePrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 21. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	Principal exists			
Post conditions	Principal is in state activated (can be authenticated).			
Use	Optional			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	activatePrincipal-Request	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_PrincipalType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	Not applicable		Not applicable	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundException		The principal to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 21: Specification of the activatePrincipal Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the activatePrincipal operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="activatePrincipalRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="principal" element="authen_requests:activatePrincipalRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.5 Specification of the deactivatePrincipal Operation

The optional deactivatePrincipal operation deactivates an existing principal. Only active principals can be authenticated.

A request to perform the deactivatePrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 22. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	Principal exists.			
Post conditions	Principal is in state deactivated (it can not be authenticated)			
Use	Optional			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	deactivatePrincipal-Request	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_PrincipalType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	Not applicable		Not applicable	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundException		The principal to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 22: Specification of the deactivatePrincipal Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the deactivatePrincipal operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="deactivatePrincipalRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="principal" element="authen_requests:deactivatePrincipalRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.6 Specification of the login Operation

The mandatory login operation initiates the validation of a certain principal for given credentials.

A request to perform the deactivatePrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 23. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	None			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	loginRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType, OA_PrincipalType and OA_CredentialsType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	OA_AuthenticationSessionInformation		Session Information that can be used to invoke services demanding authenticated principals.	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_AuthenticationFailedException		Authentication was not successful.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

	OA_PrincipalNotFoundException	The principal to act on cannot be found.
--	-------------------------------	--

Table 23: Specification of the login Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the login operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="loginRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="transactionId" element="authen_requests:loginRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="loginResponse">
  <wsdl:part name="return" element="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformation"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

4.7 Specification of the createPrincipal Operation

The mandatory createPrincipal operation creates a new principal. The parameter is a principal representation that is specific to the used authentication mechanism.

A request to perform the addPrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 24. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	The new principal is created.			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	createPrincipalRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_PrincipalType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	Not applicable		Not applicable	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 24: Specification of the createPrincipal Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the createPrincipal operation can be found in Appendix A:

XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="createPrincipalRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="newPrincipal" element="authen_requests:createPrincipalRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.8 Specification of the removePrincipal Operation

The mandatory removePrincipal operation deletes an existing principal. The principal representation is specific to the authentication mechanism used. To keep consistency the deletion of a principal should be performed within a transaction. In this transaction all references to the principal should also get deleted (e.g. group memberships, ...).

A request to perform the addPrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 25. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	Principal exists.			
Post conditions	The principal is removed and does no longer exists.			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	removePrincipalRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_PrincipalType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	Not applicable		Not applicable	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundException		The principal to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 25: Specification of the removePrincipal Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the removePrincipal operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="removePrincipalRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="principal" element="authen_requests:removePrincipalRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.9 Specification of the updatePrincipal Operation

The mandatory updatePrincipal operation updates an existing principal.

A request to perform the addPrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 26. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	The principal exists.			
Post conditions	The principal is updated.			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	updatePrincipalRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_PrincipalType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	Not applicable		Not applicable	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundException		The principal to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 26: Specification of the updatePrincipal Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the updatePrincipal operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="updatePrincipalRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="updatedPrincipal" element="authen_requests:updatePrincipalRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.10 Specification of the addCredentials Operation

The mandatory addCredentials operation adds credentials to a certain principal. Credentials are specific to the authentication mechanism used.

A request to perform the addPrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 27. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	The principal exists.			
Post conditions	The principal is associated with the specified credential object.			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	addCredentialsRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType, OA_PrincipalType and OA_CredentialsType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	Not applicable		Not applicable	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundException		The principal to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 27: Specification of the addCredentials Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the addCredentials operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="addCredentialsRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="credentialsAndPrincipal" element="authen_requests:addCredentialsRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.11 Specification of the updateCredentials Operation

The mandatory updateCredentials operation updates credentials for a certain principal.

A request to perform the addPrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 28. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	None			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	updateCredentialsRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType, OA_PrincipalType and OA_CredentialsType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	Not applicable		Not applicable	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 28: Specification of the updateCredentials Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the updateCredentials operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="updateCredentialsRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="credentialsAndPrincipal"  
element="authen_requests:updateCredentialsRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.12 Specification of the removeCredentials Operation

The optional removeCredentials operation removes credentials from a given principal.

A request to perform the addPrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 29. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	The specified principal exists and it is associated with the specified credential object.			
Post conditions	The association is removed. The principal can no longer be authenticated.			
Use	optional			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	removeCredentialsRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_PrincipalType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	Not applicable		Not applicable	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundException		The principal to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 29: Specification of the removeCredentials Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the removeCredentials operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="removeCredentialsRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="principal" element="authen_requests:removeCredentialsRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.13 Specification of the verifySessionInformation Operation

The verifySessionInformation operation determines whether the given session-information is valid.

A request to perform the addPrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 30. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	None			
Use	optional			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	verifySessionInformationRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_AuthenticatedPrincipalType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	verifySessionInformationResponse		True if the principal is valid or false otherwise.	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 30: Specification of the verifySessionInformation Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the verifySessionInformation operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="verifySessionInformationRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="sessionId" element="authen_requests:verifySessionInformationRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>  
<wsdl:message name="verifySessionInformationResponse">  
  <wsdl:part name="return" element="authen_requests:verifySessionInformationResponse"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.14 Specification of the getPrincipals Operation

The mandatory getPrincipals operation allows the retrieval of a list of principals specified by a given query.

A request to perform the getPrincipals operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 26. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	None			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	getPrincipalsRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_Query.
Returns	Type		Description	
	SequenceOfOA_PrincipalType		Set of principals matching the specified query.	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 31: Specification of the getPrincipals Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the getPrincipals operation can be found in Appendix A:

XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="getPrincipalsRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="getPrincipals" element="authen_requests:getPrincipalsRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>  
<wsdl:message name="getPrincipalsResponse">  
  <wsdl:part name="return" element="authen_types:SequenceOfOA_Principal"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

5 Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents

5.1 XML Schema Documents

The following XML Schema Documents define the data types of this service.

The XML schema documents of the used data types are bundled in a zip file with the present document and can be downloaded at https://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=20057.

In addition to XML Schema Documents specified in this appendix, this specification requires several normative XML Schema Documents. These XML Schema Documents define the common data types, e.g. common Exception Types, Basic Data Types and the GML Profile.

This file contains the XML Schema documents of the OA Basic Service and User Management Service.

The namespaces

<http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/types/1.0>,

<http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/exceptions/1.0>,

<http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/types/1.0> are used.

5.1.1 authentication_exceptions.xsd

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="windows-1252"?>
<schema xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
  xmlns:authen_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/exceptions/1.0"
  xmlns:oab_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/exceptions/1.0"
  elementFormDefault="qualified"
  targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/exceptions/1.0"
  version="1.0">
  <!--XML Schema document created by ShapeChange-->
  <element name="OA_PrincipalNotFoundException"
    substitutionGroup="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException"
    type="authen_exc:OA_PrincipalNotFoundExceptionType"/>
  <complexType name="OA_PrincipalNotFoundExceptionType">
    <complexContent>
      <extension base="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException">
        <sequence/>
      </extension>
    </complexContent>
  </complexType>
  <complexType name="OA_PrincipalNotFoundExceptionPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
      <element ref="authen_exc:OA_PrincipalNotFoundException"/>
    </sequence>
    <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink"/ -->
  </complexType>
  <element name="OA_AuthenticationFailedException"
```

```
        substitutionGroup="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException"
        type="authen_exc:OA_AuthenticationFailedExceptionType"/>
<complexType name="OA_AuthenticationFailedExceptionType">
  <annotation>
    <documentation>defined by the Authentication Service</documentation>
  </annotation>
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException">
      <sequence/>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_AuthenticationFailedExceptionPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="authen_exc:OA_AuthenticationFailedException"/>
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
</schema>
```

5.1.2 authentication_types.xsd

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="windows-1252"?>
<schema xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
        xmlns:authen_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/types/1.0"
        xmlns:ums_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/types/1.0"
        elementFormDefault="qualified"
        targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/types/1.0"
        version="1.0">
  <element name="OA_AuthenticatedPrincipal" substitutionGroup="authen_types:OA_Principal"
          type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticatedPrincipalType"/>
  <complexType name="OA_AuthenticatedPrincipalType">
    <annotation>
      <documentation>
        Represents a principal after it is authenticated. An authenticated principal consists
        of the authenticated principal as well as a time coverage the authentication is
        valid.
      </documentation>
    </annotation>
    <complexContent>
      <extension base="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType">
        <sequence>
          <element name="sessionId" type="string"/>
          <element name="validityEnd" type="dateTime"/>
        </sequence>
      </extension>
    </complexContent>
  </complexType>
  <complexType name="OA_AuthenticatedPrincipalPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
      <element ref="authen_types:OA_AuthenticatedPrincipal"/>
    </sequence>
    <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
  </complexType>
  <element name="OA_UsernamePrincipal" substitutionGroup="authen_types:OA_Principal"
          type="authen_types:OA_UsernamePrincipalType"/>
  <complexType name="OA_UsernamePrincipalType">
    <complexContent>
      <extension base="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType">
        <sequence>
          <element name="username" type="string"/>
        </sequence>
      </extension>
    </complexContent>
  </complexType>

```

Implementation Specification of the Authentication Service – Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents

```

</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_UsernamePrincipalPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="authen_types:OA_UsernamePrincipal"/>
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_PasswordCredentials" substitutionGroup="authen_types:OA_Credentials"
  type="authen_types:OA_PasswordCredentialsType"/>
<complexType name="OA_PasswordCredentialsType">
  <annotation>
    <documentation>
      Represents the principals password. The password gets stored encoded only and is
      transferred using Base64-encoding. Using Base64-Encoding prevents the occurrence of not
      valid characters within the XML documents.
    </documentation>
  </annotation>
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="authen_types:OA_CredentialsType">
      <sequence>
        <element name="password" type="string"/>
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_PasswordCredentialsPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="authen_types:OA_PasswordCredentials"/>
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>

<element name="OA_Principal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType"/>
<complexType name="OA_PrincipalType">
  <sequence>
    <element name="id" type="integer"/>
    <element name="origin" type="string"/>
    <element name="refGroups">
      <complexType>
        <sequence>
          <element name="Sequence">
            <complexType>
              <sequence>

```

```
        <element maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0" name="element"
            type="ums_types:OA_GroupPropertyType" />
    </sequence>
</complexType>
</element>
</sequence>
</complexType>
</element>
<element minOccurs="0" name="refSubject" type="ums_types:OA_SubjectPropertyType" />
<element name="active" type="boolean" />
</sequence>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_PrincipalPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
        <element ref="authen_types:OA_Principal" />
    </sequence>
    <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_Credentials" type="authen_types:OA_CredentialsType" />
<complexType name="OA_CredentialsType">
    <annotation>
        <documentation>
            Credentials e.g. used by principals in the context of Authentication Services.
        </documentation>
    </annotation>
    <sequence>
        <element name="id" type="integer" />
    </sequence>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_CredentialsPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
        <element ref="authen_types:OA_Credentials" />
    </sequence>
    <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_AuthenticationSessionInformation"
    type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType" />
<complexType name="OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType">
    <annotation>
        <documentation>
            Identifies a session and is used to determine whether the by it specified session is
            still valid.

            What shape does a SessionKey have?
        </documentation>
    </annotation>
```



```

</annotation>
<sequence>
  <element name="authenticatedPrincipals">
    <complexType>
      <sequence>
        <element name="Sequence">
          <complexType>
            <sequence>
              <element maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0" name="element"
                type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticatedPrincipalPropertyType" />
            </sequence>
          </complexType>
        </element>
      </sequence>
    </complexType>
  </element>
</sequence>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformation" />
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="SequenceOfOA_Principal" type="authen_types:SequenceOfOA_PrincipalType" />
<complexType name="SequenceOfOA_PrincipalType">
  <sequence>
    <element name="Principals">
      <complexType>
        <sequence>
          <element name="Sequence">
            <complexType>
              <sequence>
                <element name="Element"
                  type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalPropertyType"
                  minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" />
              </sequence>
            </complexType>
          </element>
        </sequence>
      </complexType>
    </element>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
</element>
</sequence>
</complexType>

```

Implementation Specification of the Authentication Service – Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents

```
<complexType name="SequenceOfOA_PrincipalPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="authen_types:SequenceOfOA_Principal"/>
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
</schema>
```

5.1.3 authentication_requests.xsd

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="windows-1252"?>
<schema xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
  xmlns:gml="http://www.opengis.net/gml"
  xmlns:authen_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/types/1.0"
  xmlns:authen_requests="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/requests/1.0"
  xmlns:oas="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/types/1.0"
  targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/requests/1.0"
  elementFormDefault="qualified"
  version="1.0">

  <element name="activatePrincipalRequest" type="authen_requests:activatePrincipalRequest"/>
  <complexType name="activatePrincipalRequest">
    <sequence>
      <element name="sessionInformation"
type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
      <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType"/>
    </sequence>
  </complexType>
  <element name="addCredentialsRequest" type="authen_requests:addCredentialsRequest"/>
  <complexType name="addCredentialsRequest">
    <sequence>
      <element name="sessionInformation"
type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
      <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType"/>
      <element name="oacredential" type="authen_types:OA_CredentialsType"/>
    </sequence>
  </complexType>
  <element name="createPrincipalRequest" type="authen_requests:createPrincipalRequest"/>
  <complexType name="createPrincipalRequest">
    <sequence>
      <element name="sessionInformation"
type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
      <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType"/>
    </sequence>
  </complexType>
  <element name="deactivatePrincipalRequest" type="authen_requests:deactivatePrincipalRequest"/>
  <complexType name="deactivatePrincipalRequest">
    <sequence>
      <element name="sessionInformation"
type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
      <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType"/>
    </sequence>
  </complexType>

```

```
</complexType>
<element name="loginRequest" type="authen_requests:loginRequest"/>
<complexType name="loginRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"
minOccurs="0"/>
    <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType"/>
    <element name="oacredential" type="authen_types:OA_CredentialsType"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="removeCredentialsRequest" type="authen_requests:removeCredentialsRequest"/>
<complexType name="removeCredentialsRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
    <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="removePrincipalRequest" type="authen_requests:removePrincipalRequest"/>
<complexType name="removePrincipalRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
    <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="updateCredentialsRequest" type="authen_requests:updateCredentialsRequest"/>
<complexType name="updateCredentialsRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
    <element name="oacredential" type="authen_types:OA_CredentialsType"/>
    <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="updatePrincipalRequest" type="authen_requests:updatePrincipalRequest"/>
<complexType name="updatePrincipalRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
    <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
```

```
<element name="verifySessionInformationRequest"
type="authen_requests:verifySessionInformationRequest"/>
<complexType name="verifySessionInformationRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
    <element name="oaauthenticatedprincipal"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticatedPrincipalType"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="verifySessionInformationResponse"
  type="authen_requests:verifySessionInformationResponse"/>
<complexType name="verifySessionInformationResponse">
  <sequence>
    <element name="isValid" type="boolean"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="getPrincipalsRequest" type="authen_requests:getPrincipalsRequest"/>
<complexType name="getPrincipalsRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInformation"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
    <element name="query" type="oas:OA_Query"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="getPrincipalsResponse" type="authen_requests:getPrincipalsResponse"/>
<complexType name="getPrincipalsResponse">
  <sequence>
    <element name="oapincipal" type="authen_types:SequenceOfOA_PrincipalType"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
</schema>
```

5.2 WSDL Document

The following WSDL Version 1.1 document is the formal specification of the Authentication Service according to rules of the “ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform”. It defines the mandatory SOAP binding.

The WSDL document is bundled in a zip file with the present document and can be downloaded at https://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=20057.

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<wSDL:definitions xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
xmlns:soap="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/soap/"
xmlns:http="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/http/"
xmlns:mime="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/mime/"
xmlns:wSDL="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/"
xmlns:authen="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService"
xmlns:authen_requests="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/requests/1.0"
xmlns:authen_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/exceptions/1.0"
xmlns:author_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/exceptions/1.0"
xmlns:authen_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/types/1.0"
xmlns:oab_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/exceptions/1.0"
xmlns:oab_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/types/1.0"
xmlns:bdt="http://eu-orchestra.org/basicTypes/1.0"
name="WSDLComponent1"
targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService">
  <wSDL:types>
    <xs:schema targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService"
      xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
      elementFormDefault="qualified"
      attributeFormDefault="qualified">
      <xs:import namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/basicTypes/1.0"
        schemaLocation="basic_types.xsd"/>
      <xs:import namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/exceptions/1.0"
        schemaLocation="oa_basic_ex.xsd"/>
      <xs:import namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/types/1.0"
        schemaLocation="oa_basic.xsd"/>
      <xs:import namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/requests/1.0"
        schemaLocation="authentication_requests.xsd"/>
      <xs:import namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/exceptions/1.0"
        schemaLocation="authorisation_exceptions.xsd"/>
      <xs:import namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/exceptions/1.0"
        schemaLocation="authentication_exceptions.xsd"/>
    </xs:schema>
  </wSDL:types>
</wSDL:definitions>
```

```

                <xs:import
orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/types/1.0"
schemaLocation="authentication_types.xsd"/>
                <xs:import
namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/types/1.0"
schemaLocation="usermanagement_types.xsd"/>
        </xs:schema>
    </wsdl:types>
    <wsdl:message name="getCapabilitiesRequest">
        <wsdl:part name="oaCapabilitiesRequest"
element="oab_types:OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest"/>
    </wsdl:message>
    <wsdl:message name="getCapabilitiesResponse">
        <wsdl:part name="oaCapabilitiesResponse"
element="oab_types:OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse"/>
    </wsdl:message>
    <wsdl:message name="activatePrincipalRequest">
        <wsdl:part name="principal" element="authen_requests:activatePrincipalRequest"/>
    </wsdl:message>
    <wsdl:message name="addCredentialsRequest">
        <wsdl:part name="credentialsAndPrincipal"
element="authen_requests:addCredentialsRequest"/>
    </wsdl:message>
    <wsdl:message name="createPrincipalRequest">
        <wsdl:part name="newPrincipal" element="authen_requests:createPrincipalRequest"/>
    </wsdl:message>
    <wsdl:message name="deactivatePrincipalRequest">
        <wsdl:part name="principal" element="authen_requests:deactivatePrincipalRequest"/>
    </wsdl:message>
    <wsdl:message name="loginRequest">
        <wsdl:part name="transactionId" element="authen_requests:loginRequest"/>
    </wsdl:message>
    <wsdl:message name="loginResponse">
        <wsdl:part name="return" element="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformation"/>
    </wsdl:message>
    <wsdl:message name="removeCredentialsRequest">
        <wsdl:part name="principal" element="authen_requests:removeCredentialsRequest"/>
    </wsdl:message>
    <wsdl:message name="removePrincipalRequest">
        <wsdl:part name="principal" element="authen_requests:removePrincipalRequest"/>
    </wsdl:message>
    <wsdl:message name="updateCredentialsRequest">
        <wsdl:part name="credentialsAndPrincipal"
element="authen_requests:updateCredentialsRequest"/>

```

```
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="updatePrincipalRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="updatedPrincipal" element="authen_requests:updatePrincipalRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="verifySessionInformationRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="sessionId"
element="authen_requests:verifySessionInformationRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="verifySessionInformationResponse">
  <wsdl:part name="return" element="authen_requests:verifySessionInformationResponse"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getPrincipalsRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="getPrincipals" element="authen_requests:getPrincipalsRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getPrincipalsResponse">
  <wsdl:part name="return" element="authen_types:SequenceOfOA_Principal"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="InvalidParameterValueFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_InvalidParameterValue"
element="oab_exc:OA_InvalidParameterValue"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="MissingParameterValueFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_MissingParameterValue"
element="oab_exc:OA_MissingParameterValue"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="NoApplicableCodeFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_NoApplicableCode" element="oab_exc:OA_NoApplicableCode"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="InternalErrorFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_InternalError" element="oab_exc:OA_InternalError"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="PrincipalNotFoundFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_PrincipalNotFoundException"
element="authen_exc:OA_PrincipalNotFoundException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="PermissionDeniedFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_PermissionDeniedException"
element="author_exc:OA_PermissionDeniedException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="AuthenticationFailedFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_AuthenticationFailedException"
element="authen_exc:OA_AuthenticationFailedException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="VersionNegotiationFailed">
```

Implementation Specification of the Authentication Service – Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents

```

        <wsdl:part name="OA_VersionNegotiationFailed"
element="oab_exc:OA_VersionNegotiationFailed"/>
    </wsdl:message>

```

```

    <wsdl:message name="UnsupportedCapSchema">
        <wsdl:part name="OA_UnsupportedCapSchema"
element="oab_exc:OA_UnsupportedCapSchema"/>
    </wsdl:message>

```

```

    <wsdl:portType name="AuthenticationService">
        <wsdl:documentation>

```

The authentication procedure depends on the actually used authentication mechanism. The necessary interactions and pieces of information vary, hence for each authentication-mechansim an individual interface needs to be specified.

One concrete usage would be to specify a UsernamePasswordAuthentication-interface and:

1. start a transaction,
2. use the concrete interface
3. call the login-operation to retrieve the session-information
4. commit the transaction.

```

    </wsdl:documentation>
    <wsdl:operation name="getCapabilities">
        <wsdl:input name="capabilitiesRequest"
message="authen:getCapabilitiesRequest"/>
        <wsdl:output name="capabilitiesResponse"
message="authen:getCapabilitiesResponse"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
message="authen:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
message="authen:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="authen:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="authen:InternalErrorFault"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="VersionNegotiationFailed"
message="authen:VersionNegotiationFailed"/>
        <wsdl:fault name="UnsupportedCapSchema"
message="authen:UnsupportedCapSchema"/>
    </wsdl:operation>
    <wsdl:operation name="verifySessionInformation">
        <wsdl:documentation>

```

The verifySessionInformation operation determines whether the given session-information is valid.

```

    </wsdl:documentation>
        <wsdl:input name="verifySessionInformationRequestRequest"
message="authen:verifySessionInformationRequest"/>
        <wsdl:output name="verifySessionInformationRequestResponse"

```

```
message="authen:verifySessionInformationResponse"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
message="authen:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
message="authen:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="authen:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="authen:InternalErrorFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="authen:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="updatePrincipal">
    <wsdl:input name="updatePrincipalRequestRequest"
message="authen:updatePrincipalRequest"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
message="authen:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
message="authen:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="authen:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="authen:InternalErrorFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="authen:PrincipalNotFoundFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="authen:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="updateCredentials">
    <wsdl:input name="updateCredentialsRequestRequest"
message="authen:updateCredentialsRequest"/>
<wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
message="authen:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
message="authen:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="authen:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="authen:InternalErrorFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="authen:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="removePrincipal">
    <wsdl:input name="removePrincipalRequestRequest"
message="authen:removePrincipalRequest"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
message="authen:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
message="authen:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="authen:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="authen:InternalErrorFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="authen:PrincipalNotFoundFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="authen:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
```

```
<wsdl:operation name="removeCredentials">
    <wsdl:input name="removeCredentialsRequestRequest"
message="authen:removeCredentialsRequest"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
message="authen:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
message="authen:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="authen:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="authen:InternalErrorFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="authen:PrincipalNotFoundFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="authen:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="login">
    <wsdl:documentation>
        Apply for authentication at an OSN.
        Input:
            The input depends on the actual authentication-mechanism, and is
hence
implementation-dependent.
        Output:
            The session of the used is returned.
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <wsdl:input name="loginRequestRequest" message="authen:loginRequest"/>
    <wsdl:output name="loginRequestResponse" message="authen:loginResponse"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
message="authen:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
message="authen:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="authen:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="authen:InternalErrorFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="authen:PrincipalNotFoundFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="authen:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="authenticationFailed"
message="authen:AuthenticationFailedFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="deactivatePrincipal">
    <wsdl:input name="deactivatePrincipalRequestRequest"
message="authen:deactivatePrincipalRequest"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
message="authen:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
message="authen:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="authen:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="authen:InternalErrorFault"/>
```

```
<wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="authen:PrincipalNotFoundFault"/>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="authen:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="createPrincipal">
  <wsdl:input name="createPrincipalRequestRequest"
message="authen:createPrincipalRequest"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
message="authen:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
message="authen:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="authen:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="authen:InternalErrorFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="authen:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="addCredentials">
  <wsdl:input name="addCredentialsRequestRequest"
message="authen:addCredentialsRequest"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
message="authen:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
message="authen:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="authen:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="authen:InternalErrorFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="authen:PrincipalNotFoundFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="authen:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="activatePrincipal">
  <wsdl:input name="activatePrincipalRequestRequest"
message="authen:activatePrincipalRequest"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
message="authen:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
message="authen:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="authen:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="authen:InternalErrorFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="authen:PrincipalNotFoundFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="authen:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="getPrincipals">
  <wsdl:input name="getPrincipalsRequestRequest"
message="authen:getPrincipalsRequest"/>
  <wsdl:output name="getPrincipalsRequestResponse"
message="authen:getPrincipalsResponse"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
```

Implementation Specification of the Authentication Service – Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents

```

message="authen:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
<wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
  message="authen:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="authen:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="authen:InternalErrorFault"/>
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="authen:PermissionDeniedFault"/>
</wsdl:operation>
</wsdl:portType>
<wsdl:binding name="AuthenticationService" type="authen:AuthenticationService">
  <wsdl:documentation>
    The authentication procedure depends on the actually used authentication
    mechanism. The necessary interactions and pieces of information vary, hence for
    each authentication-mechansim an individual interface needs to be specified.

    One concrete usage would be to specify a UsernamePasswordAuthentication-
    interface and:
    

1. start a transaction,
2. use the concrete interface
3. call the login-operation to retrieve the session-information
4. commit the transaction.


  </wsdl:documentation>
  <soap:binding style="document" transport="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/soap/http"/>
  <wsdl:operation name="getCapabilities">
    <soap:operation soapAction="getCapabilities" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
      <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:output>
      <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:output>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
      <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
      <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
      <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
      <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="UnsupportedCapSchema">
      <soap:fault name="UnsupportedCapSchema" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:operation>

```

```
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="VersionNegotiationFailed">
    <soap:fault name="VersionNegotiationFailed" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="verifySessionInformation">
    <wsdl:documentation>
```

The verifySessionInformation operation determines whether the given session-information is valid.

```
</wsdl:documentation>
    <soap:operation soapAction="verifySessionInformation" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:output>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:output>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="updatePrincipal">
    <soap:operation soapAction="updatePrincipal" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
```

```
<wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
    <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
    <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="updateCredentials">
    <soap:operation soapAction="updateCredentials" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="removePrincipal">
    <soap:operation soapAction="removePrincipal" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
```

```
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
    <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
    <soap:fault name="error4" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="removeCredentials">
    <soap:operation soapAction="removeCredentials" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="login">
    <wsdl:documentation>
        Apply for authentication at an OSN.
        Input:
        The input depends on the actual authentication-mechanism, and is
hence
```

implementation-dependent.

Output:

The session of the used is returned.

```
</wsdl:documentation>
<soap:operation soapAction="login" style="document"/>
<wsdl:input>
  <soap:body use="literal"/>
</wsdl:input>
<wsdl:output>
  <soap:body use="literal"/>
</wsdl:output>
<wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
  <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
  <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
  <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="InternalServerError">
  <soap:fault name="InternalServerError" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
  <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
  <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="authenticationFailed">
  <soap:fault name="authenticationFailed" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="deactivatePrincipal">
  <soap:operation soapAction="deactivatePrincipal" style="document"/>
  <wsdl:input>
    <soap:body use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:input>
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
    <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:fault>
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
    <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
```

```
<wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
    <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
    <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="createPrincipal">
    <soap:operation soapAction="createPrincipal" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="addCredentials">
    <soap:operation soapAction="addCredentials" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
```

```
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
    <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
    <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="activatePrincipal">
    <soap:operation soapAction="activatePrincipal" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="getPrincipals">
    <soap:operation soapAction="getPrincipals" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:output>
```

```
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:output>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
</wsdl:binding>
<wsdl:service name="AuthenticationService">
    <wsdl:port name="AuthenticationService" binding="authen:AuthenticationService">
        <soap:address
location="http://stl-d-pl1.htw-saarland.de:8080/axis2/services/AuthenticationService"/>
    </wsdl:port>
</wsdl:service>
</wsdl:definitions>
```

Implementation Specification of the Authentication Service – Appendix B: UML Model

6 Appendix B: UML Model

6.1 Static model

6.2 Dynamic model

Create a new principal

Delete a principal

Add credentials

Remove credentials

login

Implementation Specification of the Authentication Service – Appendix B: UML Model

Authentication using username-password

